

IMPACT OF TEACHERS' INCENTIVE ON PERFORMANCE OF PHYSICAL AND HEALTH EDUCATION TEACHERS

Adelekan Ebenezer Oluyemiⁱ

Department of Physical and Health Education,
Federal College of Education, Abeokuta,
Ogun State, Nigeria

Abstract:

Poor academic achievement of pupils in Nigerian primary schools together with its attendant problems has been worrisome to stakeholders in education system such that several factors like teachers' incentives and other perennial problems has been pointed to as the cause of its occurrence. This study investigates the impact of teachers' incentive on teachers' performance in primary schools in Ogun State. A descriptive survey research design and simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 teachers from both private and public schools for the study. A self-developed questionnaire was used to collect data for the study while collected data analyzed using ANOVA statistics. The findings showed that (i) there is significant difference in teachers' condition of service and teachers performance in primary school ($F(1,98) = 10.245, P < 0.05$), (ii) there is significant difference between teachers' fringe benefit and teachers performance ($F(1,98) = 8.133, P < 0.05$), (iii) the relationship between teachers' incentive and teachers' performance in primary school is positive and significant ($r = 0.146^*$ at $p < 0.05$). It was suggested that government should improve welfare packages, condition of service and other benefits of teachers.

Keywords: distance education, clothing and textiles, curriculum implementation, trainees, vocational courses

1. Introduction

Education is said to be the greatest hope and light of any nation and is quite indispensable in the growth and development of any nation. It is an instrument for sustaining the development of people, an instrument of stability, change and cultural values in a child to grow to the fullest status of a man, sound in mind and body; to acquire knowledge and skill that will enable him to live a useful life and having a standard of conduct to be trusted as well as being a man of peace, courage and sound judgment (Ilori, 2003). For a

ⁱ Correspondence: email ebenezeradelekan@gmail.com

child to be able to achieve the above mentioned values and qualities, such a child needs to be taught and trained by teachers who according to Chung & McBride (2015) develops the minds and lives of young people, facilitate teaching, help their students realize social and emotional learning. These teachers must also be adequately trained, certified and qualify for the job of teaching. Muola (2010) stated that the only way teachers could be trained and qualified for teaching is through teacher education, attained through pre-service training (achieved through university, colleges of education or polytechnic education) or in-service training (achieved through part-time and distance learning programs).

Incentive of the teachers is generally framed in the context of performance pay (bonuses), and is often used for annual evaluations (Adegoke, 2013) while some think of teacher incentives exclusively as salary and other monetary benefits. Indeed, differences in monthly pay can act as an incentive to attract and retain qualified teachers; conversely it can as well discourage qualified and talented teachers who are ready to give their service in the profession. It is imperative to also note that there are other kinds of incentives which also exist as monetary and non-monetary values, such as pensions, and other non-salary benefits that make the job of a teacher to be stable. In the present education system in Nigeria, promotions are the basic source of incentives for teachers.

Financial incentives are used in a wide range of industries, as a way to increase worker's motivation and productivity, by linking financial rewards with the output of the individual worker, the organization, or both (Lucifora & Origo, 2015). Incentives are popularly seen as a key mechanism with which to recruit, retain and motivate the workforce (Haynes, Wragg, Wragg & Chamberlin, 2003), as well as to enhance employee accountability (Hasnain, Manning & Pierskalla, 2012). Financial incentives are effective and most noticeable in workers where their output is readily observed and accurately measured; calculated based on verifiable measures of performance and effort (Gambardella, Panico & Valentini, 2013). Financial incentives on individual effort linked to pay and reward, can have a positive impact on both the quality and quantity of individual output as well as overall organizational productivity if it well designed (Friis, Hansen & Vámosi, 2014). However less clear are the effects of financial incentives on workers whose output is of a less tangible nature, harder to measure, based on knowledge or creativity, or a combination of the three (Grabner, 2014 and Kachelmeier, Reichert & Williamson, 2008).

In reference to education sector, Neal (2011) asserted that financial incentives which motivate teachers to perform to a higher standard. Based on findings, Imberman (2015) stated that evidence on individual incentives for teachers in developed countries is mixed, with some positive and some negligible impacts. The scholar stated that for developing countries, several studies indicate that incentives can be highly effective and far cheaper to implement, with innovative incentive mechanisms such as incentives based on relative student performance showing promise. Imberman (2015) further observed that in developing countries, paying teachers for student performance has been shown to be highly effective at low cost, thus incentives can effectively improve student

performance if they are designed well. Likewise, Muralidharan and Sundararaman (2011) based on their investigation observed that both group and individual incentives increased student achievement. Aire & Tella (2003) held that one of the potential methods of increasing pupils' achievement and improving quality teaching is to provide teachers with financial incentives based on pupil's achievement.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Due to economic condition of the country most states find it hard to motivate or give incentive to their teachers. This is reflected in form of rampant absenteeism, late coming, failure to assess pupils' work in time, part-time teaching in more than two schools to top up their salary, need, and satisfaction, others even teach on Saturdays and Sundays while some at night which result into examination malpractice by students and low performances among others.

This situation has raised public concern as well as negative perception of stakeholders towards the schools and ultimate goal of education in schools. In order to avoid this condition, there have been several calls for teachers to be more committed to their jobs. Teacher's incentive was seen as an important factor for increasing teachers' commitment to work as well as improving the performance of pupils, due to its impact on classroom and school activities. Hence, this study is tailored to investigate the impact of teachers' incentive on the performance of teachers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area of Ogun State.

1.2 Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant effect between condition of service of teachers and teachers' performance in Abeokuta South Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Ho₂: There is no significant effect between teachers' fringe benefit payment and teachers' performance in Abeokuta South Local Government Area of Ogun State.

Ho₃: There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' incentive and teacher's performance in Abeokuta South Local Government Area of Ogun State.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 Research Design, Population and Sample

The design used for this study is a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprises of all public and private primary school Physical and Health Education (PHE) teachers in Abeokuta South Local Government Areas, Abeokuta, Ogun State.

The researcher adopted a stratified random sampling technique to select a total of one hundred (100) PHE teachers comprising of 50 public school PHE teachers and 50 private school PHE teachers in the selected areas of study to form the sample size for this study.

2.2 Research Instruments

A self-developed questionnaire called Teacher Incentive Questionnaire (TIQ) was used to collect data for the study. The instruments used for this study was a self-developed questionnaire to obtain information from the respondents. The TIQ was divided into sections A and B. Section A deals with demographic information of the sampled teachers (e.g. age, sex, etc), while section B deals with obtaining information on teachers' incentives as it affects PHE teachers' performance. Four options with their ratings used as responses are: Strongly Agreed (4), Agreed (3), Disagreed (2) and Strongly Disagreed (1).

2.3 Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument

The face and content validation were carried out by two experts in Physical and Health Education Department. Based on their recommendation, all corrections and ambiguity were removed from the instrument, and a trial testing of the instrument was carried out on a sample of 10 teachers who were not part of the targeted sample. Using a test-retest method, a reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained for the instrument. This reliability coefficient (0.84) showed that the instrument was reliable for use.

2.4 Data Analysis

The obtained data were analyzed using One-way ANOVA which test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of SPSS statistical software packages (17.0).

3. Results and Discussion

Hypothesis One There is no significant effect between the conditions of service of teachers' and Teachers performance in primary school.

Table 1: ANOVA Analysis of Teachers performance by teachers' condition of service

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	212.996	1	212.996	10.245	0.001
Within Groups	2037.364	98	20.789		
Total	2250.360	99			

Table 1 shows the summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of PHE teachers' performance in primary school based on the teachers' condition of service. The result reveals that there is significant difference in teachers' condition of service and teachers' performance in primary school ($F_{(1, 98)} = 10.245, P < 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference between teachers' condition of service and teachers' performance in primary school was therefore rejected.

This result may have implied that teachers' performance is influenced by their condition of service. In other words, for teachers' performance to be high, they must be adequately motivated and be satisfied in a way to boost their` needs and morale which

are very important because it influences them to perform excellently to achieve the school objectives. This in turn enhances excellent performance of students academically.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant effect between teachers' fringe benefit payment and Teachers performance in primary school.

Table 2: ANOVA Analysis of teachers' performance based on teachers' fringe benefit

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	14.095	1	14.095	8.133	0.001
Within Groups	169.795	98	1.733		
Total	183.890	99			

Table 2 shows the summary of ANOVA of Teachers performance based on teachers' fringe benefit. The result reveals that there is significant difference between teachers' fringe benefit and teachers' performance ($F_{(1, 98)} = 8.133, P < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significance difference in teachers' fringe benefit and teachers' performance in primary school was therefore rejected.

Just like in Table 1, this result may have implied that teachers' performance is influenced by their fringe benefit. Benefits such as promotion leave bonus, sponsored in-service training, sponsored conferences, seminar and refresher courses, tends to increase teachers' growth and boost morale to produce more and more at higher levels. This basic consequence of this is improved students' academic performance.

Hypothesis Three: There is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' incentive and teachers' performance in primary school

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing relationship between teachers' incentive and teachers' performance in primary school

Variables	N	r	P	Remarks
Teachers' Incentive	100	0.146*	0.00	Significant
Teachers' Performance	100			

Table 3 shows the relationship that exists between teachers' incentive and teachers' performance in primary school. The correlation coefficient indicates that the relationship between teachers' incentive and teachers' performance in primary school is positive and significant ($r = 0.146^*$ at $p < 0.05$). A general overview shows that PHE teachers' incentive correlate positively with their performance in primary school.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that there is a significant difference in teachers' incentives (condition of service and fringe benefits) and teachers' performance in primary school. This therefore means that teachers' incentives have direct

impact on their performance in PHE. Similarly, the study also showed a positive and significant relationship between PHE teachers' incentives and their performance in primary school.

5. Recommendation

Based on the result of findings, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

- 1) Stakeholders should play positive roles towards setting priorities right in ensuring that teachers are given a pride of place in providing necessary impetus that would meet the challenges of the 21st century and beyond.
- 2) The concept of motivation should be given adequate attention in primary schools and uniformity should be encouraged in the educational system especially among teachers in private and government schools.
- 3) Finally, government at all levels should improve teachers' welfare packages, condition of service and other benefits, so as to raise their standard of living and make their job lucrative and nobler than what it is presently.

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